

Odisha's Resilience and Renaissance: A Comprehensive Analysis of Socio-Economic Transformation and Inclusive Policies

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Abstract: -

This research paper explores the transformative journey of the Indian state of Odisha from a region plagued by socio-economic challenges, natural disasters, and poverty to a beacon of growth and development. The narrative begins with a poignant incident in 1985, highlighting the dire circumstances faced by residents, followed by the devastating impact of the Super Cyclone in 1999. Fast-forwarding to 2023, the paper elucidates Odisha's remarkable turnaround, evidenced by a robust economic performance, with a notable 11.5% growth in Gross State Domestic Product during 2021-22.

Examining the catalyzing role of inclusive policies initiated under the leadership of Shri Navin Patnaik's government since 2000, the paper delves into key programs such as "Mission Shakti," "Mo Jami Mo Diha," and various social welfare schemes. The state's commitment to fiscal corrections and regulatory reforms for private investment is highlighted, contributing to an accelerated economic growth rate of 8.4% in recent years.

A comprehensive analysis of Odisha's strategic initiatives in various sectors, including industry, agriculture, healthcare, education, and sports, is presented. The paper emphasizes the state's focus on economic diversification, with signs of early success in sectors like IT/ITeS, hospitality, and tourism. Noteworthy advancements in infrastructure, renewable energy, and industry-specific policies are discussed, showcasing Odisha as a preferred destination for foreign direct investment.

Despite the substantial progress, the paper acknowledges existing challenges, particularly regional disparities and socio-economic inequalities. The research advocates for a holistic development strategy, emphasizing poverty alleviation, human development, and inclusive growth. The concluding remarks stress the critical juncture for Odisha to address infrastructure gaps, promote equitable distribution of growth benefits, and enhance government accountability to ensure sustained progress and improved well-being for all residents.

Key Words: Odisha, Investment Promotion, Economic Development, Policy

Introduction:

On July 31, 1985, the nation was gripped by the poignant narrative of Phanas Punji, featured in "India Today." Phanas, a resident of Ainlapalli Village in Odisha's Kalahandi district, was compelled to sell her two-year-old sister-in-law for Rs. 40 to save the lives of her two starving infants. This heart-wrenching incident was not an isolated occurrence but rather a tragically common phenomenon in the state. Kapil Narain Tiwary, the local MLA at the time, lamented, "Here, children are sold cheaper than channas (legumes)!"

On October 29, 1999, Odisha faced the wrath of the "Super Cyclone," unleashing winds at speeds of 250 KM/Hour. This natural disaster left nearly 18 million lives affected and wreaked havoc across the state's coastal districts, claiming 9,843 lives according to official records. Once again, Odisha's economy was devastated to its core.¹

Fast forward to 2023 -

The World Bank acknowledged, "Odisha's turnaround in disaster management holds valuable lessons for the world."¹

In the fiscal year 2021-22, Odisha experienced an impressive 11.5% growth in its Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP). The state's economic resilience is evident in its average medium-term growth rate of 7.9% from 2013-14 to 2021-22, excluding pandemic-affected years. According to the economic survey report, Odisha's economy is projected to grow by 7.8% in real terms, surpassing the national rate of 7% during 2022-23. Furthermore, the state is anticipated to achieve a growth rate ranging from 8 to 8.5% in real terms for the year 2023-24.²

Objective of the Study:-

1. The primary objective of this research paper is to comprehensively analyze the transformation of Odisha from a state grappling with socio-economic challenges, epitomized by incidents like the Phanas Punji case and the Super Cyclone of 1999, to its current status as a potential economic powerhouse.
2. The study aims to investigate the key policy initiatives undertaken by the government, with a particular focus on inclusive strategies that have fueled the state's remarkable economic turnaround. Through an examination of Odisha's developmental journey, the paper seeks to elucidate the pivotal role played by various schemes, such as 'Mission Shakti,' 'Mo Jami Mo Diha,' and others, in fostering sustainable growth and reducing regional disparities.

3. Additionally, the research aims to highlight the early signs of economic diversification in Odisha, shedding light on sectors experiencing growth and the challenges the state still faces in achieving widespread prosperity.
4. By exploring both opportunities and challenges, this paper aspires to contribute valuable insights into Odisha's development trajectory, providing a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing its economic and social landscape.

Ultimately, the research aims to serve as a comprehensive resource for policymakers, scholars, and practitioners interested in the dynamics of inclusive development in a state marked by resilience and aspirations, offering recommendations for future strategies to address remaining challenges and propel Odisha towards sustained progress.

Literature Review:

Inclusive Policies Focused on Growth

When the current government assumed power in 2000, led by Shri Navin Patnaik, it confronted the monumental challenge of rejuvenating one of the poorest states, often ravaged by natural calamities and periodic weather catastrophes. Initiatives kicked off with programs like "Mission Shakti" in 2001, creating over 600,000 women's self-help groups and enabling seven million women to embark on entrepreneurial journeys. In 2003, the "Matsyajibi Unnayana Yojana" provided a comprehensive welfare package for fishers, incorporating financial assistance, health/accident insurance, and support for watercraft, cages, and seaweed culture.

Subsequently, the "Mo Jami Mo Diha" aimed at safeguarding land rights for the underprivileged, aligning these efforts with development schemes. Special attention was given to aiding the impoverished, particularly those from Scheduled Tribes (ST) and Scheduled Castes (SC) communities, in retaining their land and homesteads within existing legal frameworks.³ This commitment continued with a series of government schemes such as "Banishree Yojana," "Mamata scheme," "Odisha Food Security Scheme," "Biju Yuva Shashaktikaran Yojana," "SAMPURNA," "BASUDHA," "UNNATI," "SWARNA," and more. These initiatives spanned a wide spectrum from agriculture to social welfare, healthcare to education, women's empowerment

to water supply, urban infrastructure to rural housing, tribal development to food subsidies, public transportation to energy, social security to sports and youth services, leaving no stone unturned in revitalizing overall development and empowering its citizens.

Given Odisha's fiscal challenges, the initial phase of its reform program focused on urgently needed fiscal corrections, surpassing the targets outlined in its medium-term fiscal plan (2003-08). The emphasis shifted towards supporting faster, more inclusive, and widespread economic growth. Reforms in the regulatory landscape for private investment saw substantial progress, with economic growth averaging 8.4% in recent years—outpacing the national average and nearly doubling the growth rate of the 1990s.

Odisha prioritized innovative industrial and economic policies, standing out as a pioneering state in promoting Agri-entrepreneurship to combat rural poverty. The state achieved significant milestones, ensuring electricity availability rose from 82% in 2015 to full coverage at 100% in 2019. Recent years witnessed a focus on expanding solar power, especially rooftop installations, alongside coal power development. The state assumed control of its distribution companies and established gas distribution for heating, cooking, and vehicle fuelling purposes. In 2017, IBC Solar inked a power purchase agreement (PPA) for a 20 MW plant under development in Odisha.⁴

For the fiscal year 2022-23 (BE), the State's development expenditure has surged over fourfold compared to 2011-12, aiming at fostering sustainable and inclusive growth. There's a noticeable shift from agriculture to industry and the service sector, with their shares in the Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) expected to rise to 41.3% and 36.2% respectively. The government's proactive industry initiatives like the "Make in Odisha Conclave," "Industrial Policy 2022," "Odisha Apparel and Textile Policy," "Odisha Logistic Policy 2022," "Odisha IT Policy, 2022," "Odisha Tourism Policy, 2022," "Odisha Data Centre Policy, 2022," and "Export Promotion Policy 2022" are poised to catalyze the development of a robust industrial ecosystem in Odisha.

Conversely, strategic transformations are unfolding in agriculture, with a steady uptick in crop production and productivity. Crop diversification is progressing, particularly towards climate-resilient crops. Various missions, including the "Jackfruit Mission," "Spices Mission," "Mushroom

Mission," and "Floriculture Mission," among others, introduce comprehensive and innovative interventions in different sub-sectors. The "Odisha Millet Mission," initiated in 2017-18, has been notably successful in expanding millet cultivation and promoting healthy dietary practices within communities.

Odisha's prowess in sports was highlighted by hosting the Men's Hockey World Cup 2023, showcasing significant expansions in sports infrastructure and training facilities as part of its developmental efforts. To enhance the Ease of Doing Business, the Labour and ESI Department introduced the online portal 'Par-e-Shram,' streamlining over 50 industry and labor-related services online for all commercial ventures and establishments in the state. ⁵

In summary, Odisha has not only formulated policies on paper but has also undertaken a comprehensive approach, deeply analyzing its strengths, weaknesses, and areas for development across social, economic, and cultural dimensions. Before finalizing these policies, the state has made concerted efforts to ensure their effective implementation, reaching every individual in the socio-economic spectrum. This focused approach has propelled Odisha onto a path of growth and development.

Key Policy Initiatives for Sustainable Industrial Growth in Odisha⁵:

- Odisha's Industrial Policy Resolution, 2022
- The Odisha IT Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Apparel & Technical Textiles Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Logistics Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Export Promotion Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Civil Aviation Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Tourism Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Data Centre Policy, 2022
- The Odisha Registered Vehicle Scrapping Facility Policy, 2022

Key Initiatives for Broad Basing the Industrial Sector⁵:

- Diversification / Broad basing of industries
- Support to Ancillary and Downstream Industries
- Development of enabling infrastructure
- Effective investor facilitation through GO-SWIFT 2.0
- Establishment of Industry and DIPA Care Mechanism

- Better-than-the-best incentive packages to entrepreneurs
- Boosting Innovation through Start-up Odisha

Early Indicators of Economic Diversification

Economic diversification denotes the broadening of a state's economic scope to encompass a more extensive array of goods and services. This shift is particularly significant for Odisha, given its historical reliance on agriculture and natural resources. In resource-dependent states like Odisha, economic diversification involves transitioning from a focus on agriculture and extractive industries towards manufacturing and other skill-centric sectors, such as IT/ITeS, Hospitality, and Tourism.

Signs of economic diversification in Odisha are emerging. Notably, both Indian and foreign multinational IT and ITeS companies are establishing a presence in the state. The services sector is witnessing robust growth, with an impressive rate of around 10%. Moreover, despite historical challenges like droughts and floods, the agriculture sector has exhibited a growth rate of 3% per year during 2002-07, surpassing the national average.

Consequently, Odisha's per capita income, which had progressively lagged behind the rest of India over the past five decades, is now narrowing the gap. Inequalities within Odisha are also showing signs of reduction. According to the latest National Sample Survey data, rural families in the southern region, historically one of the poorest areas without abundant mineral reserves found in the northern part of the state, are now spending up to 25% more on essentials such as food, clothing, and education for their children compared to just five years ago. While average rural spending in Odisha remains modest, it is rising at an unprecedented pace.

From October 2019 to September 2023, the top five sectors attracting FDI inflow in Odisha include the services sector, metallurgical industries, infrastructure activities, computer software and hardware, and education. Notably, Odisha secured investment intent worth Rs 10.48 lakh crore during the previous **Make in Odisha Conclave**⁷. The Government of Odisha has made targeted efforts

to attract investments across a diverse range of sectors, positioning the state as the "preferred destination" for companies in various industries.

To support the growth of these industries, the state has undertaken significant investments in the development and modernization of industrial parks, regions, and clusters. Specialized sectoral

manufacturing zones, such as the Aluminium Park, Mega Food Park, Sea Food Park, Electronics Manufacturing Cluster, PCPIR, Plastics Park, Textile Park, among others, have been established, providing essential infrastructure, water supply, and electrical connections right at the factory doorstep.

Opportunities and Challenges for Odisha's Economic Growth

Currently, the primary objective is to address substantial challenges hindering sustainable and inclusive economic growth in Odisha while simultaneously accelerating human development. The state has made significant strides in bolstering its industrial economy, excelling in both manufacturing and services, and has emerged as a prime destination for foreign direct investment (FDI). Numerous advantages make Odisha an attractive prospect for investors, including its strategic positioning and extensive coastline that enhances connectivity and trade potential, fostering extensive trade opportunities with Southeast Asian nations. The state's mineral richness forms a solid foundation for industrial growth and investment, and a young, educated workforce promotes innovation and productivity. Top-tier educational institutions ensure a continuous supply of skilled professionals, while a high standard of living at relatively low costs attracts talent and businesses to its cities. Odisha also prioritizes a safe and secure environment for businesses to flourish. Additionally, the state's rich cultural heritage adds a unique value proposition, drawing tourists and promoting cultural exchanges. Proactive and growth-oriented governance policies create an enabling environment for economic expansion.

These collective strengths present a significant opportunity for Odisha's continued economic advancement. The state is well-positioned to leverage these advantages and further propel its industrial and economic development, contributing to overall prosperity and growth.

However, Odisha grapples with substantial developmental challenges, particularly concerning regional disparities. The State Government acknowledges the imperative to address these disparities, making the removal of regional inequalities a key focus of its development strategies. Nevertheless, various economic, social, and institutional barriers have impeded the equitable distribution of development gains across all regions of Odisha. To overcome these challenges and pave the way for more inclusive growth, Odisha needs to formulate a comprehensive and well-articulated development strategy. This strategy should prioritize key areas, such as poverty alleviation and human development, building rural and urban productive infrastructure to create economic opportunities, enhancing efforts to mobilize the rural poor (with a special focus on women and vulnerable groups), encouraging private investment, public-private partnerships (PPP), and public-private-community partnerships (PPCP), emphasizing entrepreneurship opportunities across sectors, and implementing household-based micro-planning to support livelihoods, particularly in the most vulnerable regions, such as the Kalahandi-Bolangir-Koraput region.

Focusing on these key areas will enable Odisha to work towards reducing regional disparities, improving the quality of life for its citizens, and achieving sustainable and inclusive development. This endeavor will require a concerted effort from the government, private sector, civil society, and communities to drive positive change and create a more equitable and prosperous future for all residents of Odisha.

Conclusion:

Over the past two decades, Odisha has made commendable progress in governmental policies, encompassing agenda setting, policy formulation, adoption, rigorous implementation, evaluation, and maintenance. The state stands as a shining example in the country, showcasing an indigenous development model. Despite these achievements, there remains a substantial journey ahead to reach its pinnacle. Odisha, despite its advancements, retains its position as the second poorest state in the country, characterized by one of the lowest levels of urbanization. More than 45% of its population lives in poverty, with Scheduled Tribes (STs), constituting a significant 22% of the state's population, lagging behind. Geographical isolation in small villages or remote hilly areas exacerbates the poverty of many STs. Additionally, educational attainment levels are low, and the state faces a considerable burden of ill health among its populace. While Odisha has enjoyed notable success in its development journey, addressing these challenges is crucial to enhancing the quality of life for its residents and sustaining economic growth and social progress.

The recent economic growth in Odisha presents an opportune moment to consolidate past achievements and allocate public resources to build essential infrastructure. This involves bridging gaps between various segments of the population – rural and urban areas, interior regions and coastal areas, and Scheduled Tribes and the rest of the population. Policies should be tailored to unlock the full potential of sectors like agriculture, fisheries, and forestry, supporting a significant 85% of the state's population. Urgent attention is required in the education and healthcare sectors to ensure people can fully benefit from the expanding opportunities offered by the evolving economy. Substantial upgrades in roads, railways, and ports are necessary for a more equitable distribution of growth benefits and effective utilization of the state's abundant natural resources. Moreover, enhancing government accountability in delivering basic services is paramount for the successful implementation of these development initiatives.

In summary, the current situation marks a critical juncture for Odisha to address infrastructure challenges, promote inclusive growth, and enhance the well-being of its citizens. This demands a concerted effort to harness the state's potential and ensure that progress reaches all corners of society.

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